

Measurement properties of the Patient Health Questionnaire 9 items (PHQ-9) across purposes and populations worldwide: Protocol for a Living Systematic Review

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GENERAL INFORMATION:

Type and method of the review: Systematic review and meta-analysis conducted following the COSMIN guideline for systematic reviews of PROMs, and the PRISMA-COSMIN guideline for reporting systematic reviews of outcome measurement instruments (OMIs).

Condition or domain being studied: This systematic review focuses on mental health

Language: English.

Country: France.

Funding sources/sponsors: This work is part of the COLIVE-MH project funded by Wellcome under contract number C-013403.

Conflicts of interest: All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethical approval and consent to participate: This study synthesizes and analyzes data from already published studies, therefore ethical approval is not required.

Other registration details: None.

Dissemination plans: We plan to publish the review findings in a peer-reviewed journal.

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors: None.

Current review status: Ongoing.

Additional information: None.

Protocol updated on 9th February 2026

Acknowledgement: We thank Jessie Cunningham, BA (Hons); MSt (The Hospital for Sick Children) for peer review of the submitted search strategy, and Catherine Auzimour for the project management.

Introduction

The Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) is one of the most frequently used patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) for assessing depressive symptoms in both research and clinical practice. Developed by Kroenke and colleagues in 2001 (Kroenke, Spitzer, & Williams, 2001) as part of the broader Patient Health Questionnaire (Spitzer et al., 1999), it operationalises the nine diagnostic criteria for major depressive disorder listed in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders IV (DSM-IV). These criteria are represented by nine self-reported items rated on a four-point scale based on symptom frequency over the past two weeks, yielding a total score ranging from 0 to 27. The tool was designed with the dual purpose of assessing symptom severity and, based on cut-off scores, detecting major depression (Kroenke et al., 2001; Kroenke & Spitzer, 2002; Levis, Benedetti, & Thombs, 2019). Because of its brevity, conceptual clarity, and ease of administration, the PHQ-9 is widely used for screening and for monitoring depressive symptoms over time in clinical practice and research (von Glischinski et al., 2021; Veal et al., 2024; Sprenger et al., 2026). Its uptake in clinical research has been further encouraged by recent international initiatives to promote the use of a set of common outcome measures to reduce measurement heterogeneity and improve comparability across studies (Obbarius et al., 2017; Farber et al., 2023).

Although the PHQ-9 is widely used, several substantive concerns have been raised about its measurement properties. Important concerns pertain to content validity, with evidence suggesting that most depression scales, including the PHQ-9, may not fully capture domains that matter to individuals with lived experience of depression (Chevance et al., 2020). Moreover, recent research indicates that instructions and items may be misinterpreted by the respondents, particularly in clinical samples (Panayiotou et al., 2025). Another concern relates to inconsistent findings for structural validity. Although the PHQ-9 was originally conceptualised as a unidimensional measure of depressive symptom severity, evidence has been mixed (Lamela et al., 2020), with some studies reporting alternative factor structures (Fried et al., 2016; Guo et al., 2017) and others supporting unidimensionality (González-Blanch et al., 2018; Keum et al., 2018). Evidence for measurement invariance is also inconsistent across cultural and demographic groups, with some studies reporting that PHQ-9 items and scores function equivalently across groups (Sucitra et al., 2025; González-Blanch et al., 2018; Harry & Waring, 2019), while others identify partial invariance or differential item functioning, indicating that some items may behave differently across populations (Baas et al., 2011; Murray et al. 2022; Grupp et al., 2020).

When primary studies yield heterogeneous and sometimes conflicting results, interpretation requires a synthesis that integrates findings across populations, settings, and methodological approaches. However, previous systematic reviews have often focused on specific populations or settings, such as perinatal depression (e.g., Wang et al., 2021), primary care patients (e.g., Costantini et al., 2021), or resource-constrained settings (e.g., Carroll et al., 2020), or they have typically examined only a limited subset of measurement properties, such as internal consistency and reliability (e.g., Ajele & Idemudia, 2025; Chae et al., 2025). As a result, the available evidence remains dispersed across reviews that differ in scope, populations, and evaluated measurement domains, limiting comparability and comprehensive understanding of overall instrument performance.

Inconsistencies observed in the findings of primary studies and reviews may reflect true differences in the PHQ-9's performance across populations, settings, or cultural backgrounds, but they may also arise from heterogeneity in how measurement properties are defined, operationalised, and assessed, as well as from the lack of shared terminology and methodological standards in health measurement (Mokkink et al., 2009; Mokkink et al., 2010). This variation contributes to divergent findings and limits comparability across studies, highlighting the need for synthesis based on consistent and transparent methodological standards.

Most existing reviews are also static in nature. Given the increasing adoption of the PHQ-9 as a common outcome measure, new validation studies are expected to continue emerging across diverse populations and settings, making static syntheses rapidly outdated (Elliot et al., 2017; Shojania et al., 2007). In addition, even when high-quality syntheses are available, their findings are not always effectively communicated or accessible to researchers, clinicians, and other interest-holders, which limits their uptake and impact. Open platforms for summarising and disseminating evidence have been proposed as a way to improve transparency, accessibility, and knowledge translation across audiences (Gosling et al., 2024). In the context of depression measurement, previous initiatives have demonstrated the value of such platforms. For instance, the DEPRESSion Screening Data (DEPRESSD) Collaboration (<https://www.depressd.ca/>) disseminates evidence on the performance of depression instruments for screening purposes, including the PHQ-9 (Negeri et al., 2021).

To address these challenges, the present study adopts a living systematic review approach to examine the measurement properties of the PHQ-9 across populations, settings, and cultural backgrounds. By continuously incorporating newly published evidence using a standardised methodological framework, the review aims to maintain an up-to-date and coherent evidence base as the literature evolves. The review will be conducted using the taxonomy (Mokkink et al., 2010) and guidance developed by the COSMIN initiative (COnsensus-based Standards for the selection of health Measurement INstruments) (Mokkink et al., 2024), which provides standards for evaluating study and instrument quality. In parallel, the results will be integrated into an open-access, continuously updated platform that presents the evidence in a structured and accessible format to support transparency, comparison across contexts, and knowledge translation.

The findings will inform users about the measurement properties of the PHQ-9 across purposes of use, populations, and settings. They will also help determine whether reported inconsistencies reflect systematic and interpretable patterns across groups and contexts. By applying consistent methodological standards and updating the evidence base on an ongoing basis, this review will improve the comparability, transparency, and cumulative value of evidence on the PHQ-9's measurement properties.

Methods

1. Objectives

1. The primary objective of this project is twofold:
 - (i) to systematically identify, appraise, and synthesise all available evidence on the measurement properties, as defined by the COSMIN framework, of the PHQ-9 in measuring depressive symptoms, across purposes (e.g., outcome measure of treatment effect, screening) and populations worldwide, using a living evidence synthesis approach; and
 - (ii) to disseminate this evidence through an open access, regularly updated and user-friendly web-based platform to support researchers, clinicians, people with lived experiences and other interest-holders in the informed selection and use of the scale.

2. The secondary objectives are:
 - (i) to evaluate the feasibility of implementing the PHQ-9 in clinical and research settings;
 - (ii) to describe the interpretability of its scores; and
 - (iii) to identify and highlight key research gaps.

This protocol is part of COLIVE-MH, a broader project designed to build a regularly updated platform on the measurement properties of the four PROMs recommended by the Common Measures in Mental Health Science Initiative (CMMHS) (Farber et al., 2023): PHQ-9, the Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7 item scale (GAD-7), the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0), and the Revised Child Anxiety and Depression Scale 25 items (RCADS-25). It follows the methodological framework described in the COLIVE-MH Master Protocol. The project involves international teams of researchers in clinical epidemiology, psychiatry and anthropology, and co-researchers with lived experience.

2. Study Design and Reporting Guidelines

The protocol of this systematic review follows the PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Protocols) guidelines (Moher et al., 2015) and will be prospectively registered on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Protocol deviations and amendments will be listed in the Supplementary materials of any future publications. The publication of the results of the systematic reviews will be reported following the PRISMA-COSMIN for OMs reporting guidelines (Elsman et al., 2024), and given its living modality, we will also adhere to the PRISMA-LSR extension (Akl et al., 2024). The involvement of experts with lived experience will be reported following the GRIPP-2 framework (Staniszewska et al., 2017).

The development and peer review of the search strategy will follow the PRESS (Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies) 2015 guidelines (McGowan et al., 2016). The systematic reviews of measurement properties will be conducted according to the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024), which includes recommendations for measurement properties evidence synthesis

and quality appraisal. In addition, the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Diagnostic Test Accuracy (Deeks et al., 2023) and the QUADAS-2 (Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies) guidelines (Schueler et al., 2012) will be consulted for additional guidance when evaluating the PHQ-9 performance as a screening or diagnostic tool.

3. Formulation of the research question

Construct: In the present review we focus on studies that are using the PHQ-9 to measure the construct it purports. PHQ-9 was developed to measure depression and depressive symptoms as defined by the DSM. It was not developed to measure the lived experience of depression, or well-being, or other construct, even if some studies might have extended its use.

Population: There will not be any restrictions on population characteristics. We will include all ages (children to elderly person), genders, sex, nationalities, languages, countries, cultural backgrounds, and settings. This includes clinical (physical and mental health) and non-clinical populations. Evidence syntheses based on COSMIN guidelines will be conducted on populations defined by clinical and sociodemographical categories.

Type of instrument: Version of PHQ-9 used (including adaptations made into different cultures and languages).

Measurement properties (based on the COSMIN framework, with adaptations):

1. Content validity
2. Structural validity
3. Internal consistency
4. Cross-cultural validity / measurement invariance
5. Reliability
6. Measurement error
7. Criterion validity
8. Diagnostic and screening accuracy
9. Hypothesis testing for construct validity
10. Responsiveness

Other properties:

11. Feasibility
12. Interpretability
13. Acceptability

Studies: We will include primary studies regardless of their design, as eligibility will be determined by the presence of evaluable evidence on measurement properties rather than by study design labels.

4. Pilot Feasibility Study

Before drafting the current protocol, we conducted a pilot study to evaluate the feasibility of the project and inform strategic decisions. This pilot study was conducted by running searches in PubMed, PsycINFO, and Embase (from inception to 1st November 2025), using a preliminary version of the search string. This preliminary search resulted in 25,969 records retrieved from the bibliographic databases, which was reduced to 18,236 after duplicates were removed. Two reviewers independently screened by title and abstract a sample of 312 studies. Of these, 24 (7%) were included in the phase of full-text review, out of which 15 (5%) were deemed eligible for the systematic review. The search strings, exact procedures, results, and insights derived from the pilot study are provided in Appendix A.

The pilot study allowed us to refine the search strings, eligibility criteria, and procedures for screening and data extraction. Further, it provided us with preliminary estimates on the number of studies expected to be included. Based on the estimates of inclusion rates in the pilot, we would expect 1300 studies for full-text review, out of which 900 would be included in the systematic review.

5. Eligibility criteria

Studies will be included if they meet the following inclusion criteria:

1. Peer-reviewed articles examining at least one or more measurement properties or describing the interpretability or feasibility of the PHQ-9. Articles in which measurement properties evaluation is stated as an objective of the paper and report results on measurement properties in the methods or results section will be included.
 - a. The construct of interest is depression or depressive symptomatology, consistent with the original conceptualisation and intended use of the PHQ-9 (Kroenke et al., 2001). If articles do not specify the construct, they aim to measure with the PHQ-9, we will consider that they are measuring the original construct (depression as defined by the DSM), if this is consistent with the whole article.
 - b. Measurement properties will be defined according to the COSMIN taxonomy (Mokkink et al., 2010; Mokkink et al., 2024), with adaptations, as specified in table 1. Any statistical methods of analysis will be included (e.g., Classic test theory, Item Response theory). Definitions of all measurement properties are provided in Table 1, and further operationalized in Appendix B.
 - c.
2. No restrictions on population characteristics. We will include all ages (from children to elderly people), sexes/genders, languages, countries, cultural backgrounds, or settings; including clinical (physical and mental health) and non-clinical populations.
3. Any adaptation of the original PHQ-9 will be considered, as long as it maintains the original item content (i.e., including the 9 depression symptoms explored in 9 items). For example, adaptations to other cultural backgrounds (e.g., Arabic version, AlHadi et al., 2017) or populations (e.g., Adolescent version, Aggarwal et al. 2017) will be included. Modifications in the wording of items will also be allowed, as long as the meaning is not substantially

changed. These modifications will be explicitly recorded and considered in the data extraction and synthesis.

4. We will include all self-report formats, electronic, paper, or read-aloud or interview version of the PHQ-9, as long as the participant is the main respondent and there is no judgment or influence by a person administering the instrument to the participant. Populations with severe impairment will be included if individuals can independently understand, interpret and respond to the PHQ-9.
5. We will include primary studies of any design, as eligibility will be determined by the presence of evaluable measurement properties evidence rather than by study design alone. This includes instrument development and validation studies, cross-sectional, longitudinal observational studies, and clinical studies or randomized trials reporting analyses on measurement properties. Qualitative studies in which participants from any population (e.g., individuals with lived experiences of depression, clinicians, caregivers, or members of the general population) will be also included if they report evidence on measurement properties (e.g., content validity, development paper) or other properties of the tool (e.g., acceptability, feasibility, interpretability).

Table 1. *Definitions of measurement properties and other properties of the measurement tool.*

Measurement properties and other properties of the tools	Definition
<i>1. Content validity</i>	The degree to which the content of a PROM is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured.
<i>2. Structural validity</i>	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured.
<i>3. Internal consistency</i>	The degree of the interrelatedness among the items.
<i>4. Cross-cultural validity / measurement invariance</i>	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted PROM are an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the PROM.
<i>5. Reliability</i>	The proportion of the total variance in the measurements which is due to ‘true’ ¹ differences between respondents. It indicates an instrument’s ability to distinguish between individuals - with various scores and despite measurement error (Mokkink et al., 2023; 2026).
<i>6. Measurement error</i>	The systematic and random error of a respondent’s score that is not attributed to true changes in the construct to be measured. It refers to how similar or close the scores are from repeated measurements in an individual who is stable on the outcome of interest (Mokkink et al., 2023; 2026).

7. <i>Criterion validity</i>	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of a 'gold standard'.
8. <i>Diagnostic and screening accuracy</i>	The ability of the PROM to correctly classify study participants, as having the target disorder or not. In most cases, that information will be relevant when the PROM is considered for diagnostic reasons (to identify the disorder that most likely is responsible for the signs and symptoms of the patient) or for screening purposes (to identify patients with unrecognised depression).
9. <i>Hypothesis testing for construct validity</i>	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are consistent with hypotheses (regarding relationships to scores of other instruments, or differences between relevant groups) based on the assumption that the PROM validly measures the construct to be measured.
10. <i>Responsiveness</i>	The ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured.
11. <i>Feasibility</i> ²	Ease of application of the PROM in its intended context of use, given constraints such as time or money.
12. <i>Interpretability</i> ²	The degree to which one can assign qualitative meaning - that is, clinical or commonly understood connotations – to a PROM's quantitative scores or change in scores.
13. <i>Acceptability</i> ²	How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.

Notes: The definitions of the measurement properties are based on the COSMIN taxonomy, extracted from the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024). The Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Diagnostic Test Accuracy will be used where appropriate to supplement the COSMIN guidance (Deeks et al., 2023).

¹ The word 'true' must be seen in the context of the CTT, which states that any observation is composed of two components – a true score and error associated with the observation. 'True' is the average score that would be obtained if the scale were given an infinite number of times. It refers only to the consistency of the score, and not to its accuracy (Streiner & Norman, 2008).

² Feasibility, interpretability and acceptability are not considered a measurement property, but important aspects when selecting measurement instruments. Acceptability was added specifically to this project and the definition will be refined according to the literature identified during the systematic review.

The following exclusion criteria will be applied:

1. We will exclude non-peer reviewed outputs, such as conference abstracts, posters, dissertations and other short communications.
2. Studies in which the PHQ-9 is used solely as a comparator to evaluate another instrument, or only as a predictor, grouping variable, or prevalence estimator, without any examination of the measurement properties of the PHQ-9 itself, will be excluded.
3. Case studies will be excluded because they do not provide enough information to evaluate measurement properties.

Some of the studies that do not meet our eligibility criteria will be systematically identified and tagged under predefined categories during the entire screening process, from title and abstract

to full-text selection. These studies fall outside the primary scope of the present review but are relevant for parallel projects, methodological insight, or contextual interpretation of the literature:

4. Potential Clinician-Reported Outcome Measure (ClinROM) and the Observer-Reported Outcome Measure (ObsROM) versions of PHQ-9 will be excluded if they were used to capture the perspective or experience of clinicians/observers, rather than the respondents.
5. Studies investigating the effects of administering the PHQ-9 on individuals, groups, or settings, such as psychological impact, behavioural consequences, or social effects. These studies focus on consequences of measurement rather than on examining measurement properties. They will be integrated in an ancillary scoping review.
6. Studies providing conceptual, methodological, or implementation-oriented insights into the use of the PHQ-9, for example studies examining barriers and facilitators to uptake, training strategies for clinicians, or integration into routine care or digital systems. They will be used to guide the website interface of the platform.
7. Studies examining the PHQ-9 alongside other measures to generate cross-walks, linking functions or score equivalence across instruments. The primary focus of these studies is on mathematical comparability across scales rather than on examining the measurement performance of the targeted PROMs itself (e.g., a score of 5 in PHQ-9 = 7 in the BDI).
8. Studies in which the PHQ-9 is used to measure a construct that does not clearly correspond to depression/depressive symptomatology will be excluded from the measurement properties synthesis. For example, studies aiming to measure well-being, general mental health, or other constructs with the PHQ-9.
9. Systematic reviews summarising evidence on measurement properties of the PHQ-9, either alone or in comparison with other depression measures. These reviews will not be included as primary evidence but will be reviewed to cross-check coverage of primary studies and to support identification of additional eligible studies.
10. Studies examining shortened, extended or modified versions of the PHQ-9 in which the content of the original items has been modified (e.g., PHQ-8, PHQ-2). This includes modifications to response options (e.g., alternative response formats), scoring algorithms (e.g., alternative ways of summing the items into a total score), cut-off thresholds (e.g., exploring different thresholds than the originally validated), instructions for completion (e.g., more developed or specific instructions than the originally provided) or recall period (e.g., experience in the last week instead of the last two weeks).

6. Search strategy

To identify relevant studies, we will conduct systematic searches in major bibliographic databases: MEDLINE via PubMed, CINAHL via EBSCO, Embase via Elsevier, Web of Science via Clarivate, PsycInfo via EBSCO. Grey literature will not be searched. Although grey literature can provide relevant content to increase the comprehensiveness of a review and reduce publication bias, the systematic review aims to map and synthesize peer reviewed studies only to ensure the feasibility and quality of the overall project. We acknowledge that restricting inclusion to peer-reviewed literature may result in the omission of locally produced knowledge, rare

language adaptations, and context-specific validation studies that are not indexed in major international bibliographic databases.

The searches will be conducted from 1st January 1995 until 20th January 2026. The lower bound was chosen to allow a 4-year margin prior to the first development paper of the PHQ-9 (published in 1999). An update of the searches will be conducted on July 1st, 2026, and thereafter, updated every 3 months.

The search strategy is structured around two main concept blocks: (1) the PHQ-9 and (2) measurement properties. These blocks will be combined using the Boolean operator AND. The PHQ-9 block is instrument-focused and does not include disorder-related terms. The measurement properties block is based on a validated search filter developed by the COSMIN group to identify studies on measurement properties (Terwee et al., 2009; <https://www.cosmin.nl/tools/pubmed-search-filters/>), which was supplemented with additional keywords across all measurement properties. Database-specific subject headings (e.g., MeSH, Emtree) and syntax were used where applicable.

The search strategy was initially developed by the review team. It was then reviewed and translated for all bibliographic databases by two information specialists from Université Paris Cité, France. Finally, the full search strategy underwent independent peer review by an external information specialist from the Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Canada, in accordance with the PRESS 2015 guidelines (McGowan et al., 2016), prior to execution. The search strategies are provided in Appendix C.

In addition, the reference lists of included primary studies and relevant systematic reviews will be screened to identify any additional eligible studies. Citation tracking tools (e.g. Research Rabbit <https://www.researchrabbit.ai/>) will also be used to identify related studies, including forward and backward citations of included articles.

7. Screening procedure

Records will be imported into the Sustainable Knowledge (SK) platform developed by Epistemonikos as part of its end-to-end system for deduplication and reference management (Rada et al., 2020; <https://www.skplatform.org>). The platform will also be used for the screening process. Two independent reviewers will screen all records by title and abstract. Discrepancies will be resolved by a third reviewer. All studies retrieved as full text will be subsequently reviewed by two reviewers for its final inclusion in the systematic review. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion, and if necessary, involving a third reviewer. The study selection process will be documented using a PRISMA 2020 flow diagram, and a list of studies excluded at the full-text stage, together with reasons for exclusion, will be provided.

8. Sequential approach for data extraction and synthesis

Data extraction and synthesis will be organized in a workflow of two sequential and complementary phases:

1) Phase A: Living Mapping of the Measurement Evidence Base

In this initial phase we will systematically map the available evidence by identifying all articles that report one or more studies on measurement properties of the PHQ-9 or report on the interpretability of the PHQ-9 and classifying their broad characteristics (including study features, instrument characteristics (e.g., language version used), participant characteristics, and the measurement properties assessed).

2) Phase B: Living Evidence Syntheses of the Measurement Properties

In this phase we will conduct sequenced COSMIN-guided systematic reviews on specific populations and intended instrument uses. The reviews will synthesise and rate the quality of the results, assess risk of bias, and grade the certainty of evidence.

The outputs of Phase A and Phase B will be disseminated in an open-access platform with summaries, visualisations, and structured syntheses of measurement properties across contexts. The project will expose evidence gaps across populations, settings, and measurement properties, informing areas where future primary research is needed. In addition, we will identify potential areas for improvement of the PHQ-9.

9. Phase A: Living Mapping of the Evidence

Data extraction. All studies meeting the inclusion criteria after full-text screening will undergo structured data extraction within the Epistemonikos end-to-end system. Two reviewers will independently extract data. All the reviewers involved in the screening will train on 10% of the included studies. The codebook for data extraction for the Living Mapping phase is provided in Appendix D. For each study, data will be collected across eight broad categories:

- A. **Study metadata:** Study ID, year of publication, journal, DOI, etc.
- B. **Study characteristics:** Design of the study, inclusion criteria with threshold, etc.
- C. **Characteristics of the PHQ-9:** Exact version of the instrument used, administration mode (self-administered, read-aloud, etc.), format (Paper/pencil, online, etc.), different languages and cultural adaptations (e.g., translated to Arabic), or other adaptations (e.g., Adolescent version), etc.
- D. **Purpose of use** for which the properties of the PHQ-9 are being examined (outcome assessment, screening/diagnostic).
- E. **Participant characteristics:** Sociodemographic (age, gender/sex, and country, specific demographics such as prisoners, migrants, etc) and clinical characteristics (e.g., general population, physical illness, mental health condition), etc.
- F. **Measurement properties:** At this stage, we will only classify which measurement properties are examined in each article. Measurement properties will be classified based on the analyses and statistics reported in the primary studies, following COSMIN guidance. Definitions of all measurement properties are listed in Table 1, and examples of commonly reported analyses and indicators are operationalized in Appendix B.

- G. **Other properties of the tool:** Studies reporting evidence on the feasibility, interpretability and/or acceptability of the PHQ-9 will be also classified accordingly.
- H. **Involvement of contributors with lived experiences:** We will extract information on whether individuals with lived experiences actively contributed to each included study, beyond the role of participants.

The data extraction form will be pilot tested on a subset of random included studies to ensure completeness and consistency. In the context of a living systematic review, both the extraction form and the dataset will be updated on an ongoing basis as new evidence emerges.

Data synthesis. The data extraction of this phase will allow us to map the available evidence and to inform the organization of Phase B. The data will be analysed with descriptive statistics, and all outputs will be displayed in the open-access platform.

10. Phase B: Living Evidence Syntheses of the PHQ-9 Properties

Phase B will synthesize evidence on PHQ-9 measurement properties following COSMIN guidance. We will first extract and assess PHQ-9 characteristics from its original development studies to define their measurement scope and support the later assessment of content validity. We will conduct sequenced COSMIN-guided systematic reviews in populations with diverse clinical and sociodemographic characteristics (for instance properties of the PHQ-9 for screening pregnant women). The sequence of the review will be defined according to the availability of evidence as identified by the living evidence mapping conducted in Phase A, input from project collaborators, including scientific with different expertise and lived experts. All systematic reviews will be conducted using harmonised methods to facilitate comparison and integration of findings across reviews.

For each review, we will extract data on all reported measurement properties and other properties (e.g., interpretability) of the PHQ-9. We will assess the methodological quality of included studies, evaluate results against COSMIN criteria for good measurement properties, summarise findings (including quantitative pooling where appropriate), and assess the certainty of evidence using GRADE. Adapting and refining both the COSMIN risk of bias checklist and the GRADE criteria for certainty of synthesised evidence of measurement properties are part of the present project. These projects will be detailed in other research protocols.

Further details on the procedures for the evidence syntheses are reported in the Master Protocol of the COLIVE-MH project.

11. Living systematic review methodology

This review is designed as a living systematic review. Following the initial search, literature searches will be updated after 6 months to allow enough time for the initial screening and data extraction, and then on at subsequent intervals of 3 months. However, frequency of updates may

be adapted based on the amount of evidence and the available resources. At each update, newly identified records will undergo title and abstract screening and full-text assessment using the same eligibility criteria and standardized methodological procedures as those applied in the initial review. The newly identified eligible studies through these updates will be included in the data extraction syntheses of Phase A and B. Every update will be disseminated in partnership through the Epistemonikos platform for Interactive Evidence Synthesis (<https://www.skplatform.org>).

The review is planned to remain in living mode for a period of 2 years starting from the date of the first search. Retirement from the living mode will be considered based on prespecified criteria, including stability of conclusions across updates (e.g., reaching High GRADE), or reduced relevance of the review question. If none of these criteria are met at the end of the planned period, the need for continuing the updates will be reassessed.

12. Ethics and Dissemination

As this study synthesizes existing literature, no ethical approval will be required. The protocol will be prospectively registered on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), and all protocol deviations will be transparently reported in the Supplementary Materials of the respective peer-reviewed publications issued from this living systematic review. Findings will be disseminated through peer-reviewed open-access publications, national and international conference presentations. Results will be hosted on an open-access living evidence platform which development will be described elsewhere.

13. Lived experience engagement

We consider the engagement of people with lived experiences of mental health conditions as key to this project since the PHQ-9 and the three other measurement tools intend to measure mental health symptoms through self-reported evaluation of symptoms. As of 9th February 2026, the engagement plan is still under development with people with lived experiences from different countries and with different backgrounds. This protocol has been developed with two co-researchers with lived experiences and background in psychology and is under review by three lived experts with background in anthropology. Their feedback will be implemented in the next version. The next update of this protocol will display the precise procedures of engagement at each stage of the LSR.

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Appendix A: Pilot Feasibility study for PHQ-9

Purpose of the pilot study:

To refine the methodology of the living systematic review, we conducted a pilot study focused on identifying the most effective way to screen and extract relevant information and psychometric evidence on the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9). The pilot was designed to assess the feasibility of our search strategy, screening workflow, inclusion/exclusion criteria and test data extraction procedures, guided by COSMIN recommendations.

Scoping work and development of search strategy:

We began by reviewing existing systematic reviews on the PHQ-9 to understand how authors structured their searches, developed search terms, and reported measurement properties, including how they applied frameworks such as COSMIN and QUADAS. This scoping work informed the development of our initial COSMIN-informed search strategy.

The following databases were searched from inception till the 1st of November 2025:

- a. PubMed
- b. PsycINFO
- c. Embase

using a two-block structure:

- Block 1: PHQ-9-related keywords
- Block 2: COSMIN filter for measurement properties (Terwee et al. 2009).

Attached below is the final search string developed and utilised for the pilot study (search string provided for PubMed as an example):

PubMed

#1 (PHQ*[Title/Abstract] OR patient health questionnaire*[Title/Abstract])

AND

#2 (instrumentation[sh] OR methods[sh] OR "Validation Study"[pt] OR "Comparative Study"[pt] OR "Psychometrics"[MeSH Terms] OR psychometr*[tiab] OR clinimetr*[tw] OR clinometr*[tw] OR "Outcome Assessment, Health Care"[MeSH Terms] OR "outcome assessment"[tiab] OR "outcome measure*" [tw] OR "observer variation"[MeSH Terms] OR "observer variation"[tiab] OR "Health Status Indicators"[MeSH Terms] OR "reproducibility of results"[MeSH Terms] OR reproducib*[tiab] OR "discriminant analysis"[MeSH Terms] OR reliab*[tiab] OR unreliab*[tiab] OR valid*[tiab] OR "coefficient of variation"[tiab] OR coefficient[tiab] OR homogeneity[tiab] OR homogeneous[tiab] OR "internal consistency"[tiab] OR (cronbach*[tiab] AND (alpha[tiab] OR alphas[tiab])) OR (item[tiab] AND (correlation*[tiab] OR selection*[tiab] OR reduction*[tiab])) OR agreement[tw] OR precision[tw] OR imprecision[tw] OR "precise values"[tw] OR test-retest[tiab] OR (test[tiab] AND retest[tiab]) OR (reliab*[tiab] AND (test[tiab] OR retest[tiab])) OR stability[tiab]

OR interrater[tiab] OR inter-rater[tiab] OR intrarater[tiab] OR intra-rater[tiab] OR intertester[tiab] OR inter-tester[tiab] OR intratester[tiab] OR intra-tester[tiab] OR interobserver[tiab] OR inter-observer[tiab] OR intraobserver[tiab] OR intra-observer[tiab] OR intertechnician[tiab] OR inter-technician[tiab] OR intratechnician[tiab] OR intra-technician[tiab] OR interexaminer[tiab] OR inter-examiner[tiab] OR intraexaminer[tiab] OR intra-examiner[tiab] OR interassay[tiab] OR inter-assay[tiab] OR intraassay[tiab] OR intra-assay[tiab] OR interindividual[tiab] OR inter-individual[tiab] OR intraindividual[tiab] OR intra-individual[tiab] OR interparticipant[tiab] OR inter-participant[tiab] OR intraparticipant[tiab] OR intra-participant[tiab] OR kappa[tiab] OR kappas[tiab] OR repeatab*[tw] OR ((replicab*[tw] OR repeated[tw]) AND (measure[tw] OR measures[tw] OR findings[tw] OR result[tw] OR results[tw] OR test[tw] OR tests[tw])) OR generaliza*[tiab] OR generalisa*[tiab] OR concordance[tiab] OR (intraclass[tiab] AND correlation*[tiab]) OR discriminative[tiab] OR "known group"[tiab] OR "factor analysis"[tiab] OR "factor analyses"[tiab] OR "factor structure"[tiab] OR "factor structures"[tiab] OR dimension*[tiab] OR subscale*[tiab] OR (multitrait[tiab] AND scaling[tiab] AND (analysis[tiab] OR analyses[tiab])) OR "item discriminant"[tiab] OR "interscale correlation*" [tiab] OR error[tiab] OR errors[tiab] OR "individual variability"[tiab] OR "interval variability"[tiab] OR "rate variability"[tiab] OR (variability[tiab] AND (analysis[tiab] OR values[tiab])) OR (uncertainty[tiab] AND (measurement[tiab] OR measuring[tiab])) OR "standard error of measurement"[tiab] OR sensitiv*[tiab] OR responsive*[tiab] OR (limit[tiab] AND detection[tiab]) OR "minimal detectable concentration"[tiab] OR interpretab*[tiab] OR ((minimal[tiab] OR minimally[tiab] OR clinical[tiab] OR clinically[tiab]) AND (important[tiab] OR significant[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR (small*[tiab] AND (real[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR "meaningful change"[tiab] OR "ceiling effect"[tiab] OR "floor effect"[tiab] OR "Item response model"[tiab] OR IRT[tiab] OR Rasch[tiab] OR "Differential item functioning"[tiab] OR DIF[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "item bank"[tiab] OR "cross-cultural equivalence"[tiab])

Screening process:

For completeness, the inclusion criteria included empirical studies examining at least one measurement property of the PHQ-9 or reported on the interpretability or feasibility of the PHQ-9 in any study design, population, clinical setting or country.

A PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1), summaries the screening process below.

A sample of 312 records was selected based on the surname of the first author of the primary study (starting with the letter A) and screened at the title and abstract level., Of these, 24 (7%) progressed to full-text review, of which 15 (5%) were deemed eligible for the systematic review.

Our exclusion criteria, during both the title/abstract and full-text screening included:

1. Non-peer reviewed publications (e.g. dissertations, conference abstracts).
2. Studies that did not evaluate any measurement properties or evaluated or described any interpretability or feasibility aspects of the PHQ-9.
3. Studies evaluating non-standard versions of the PHQ-9 (e.g. PHQ-2, PHQ-8).

- Studies that utilised the PHQ-9 as a comparator instrument for the validation of other measures of depression/mental health.

Note: Systematic reviews were not included for our study but tagged to provide an overview of the existing literature and utilise them as a base for additional studies that could otherwise be undetectable by our search.

Figure 1:

PRISMA flowchart representing screening process for pilot study on the PHQ-9

Data extraction:

Data extraction was completed for a random sample of 7 studies from the 15 that were deemed as eligible. Extracted information included general study and participant characteristics, such as

sample size, population demographics, and country where the study was conducted, PHQ-9 version and administration format, and measurement properties assessed in the study. The table below (Table 1) provides a summary of the data extracted during our pilot study.

Table 1

Summary of the included studies.

Study	Population	N	Version of PHQ-9	Country	Measurement properties examined
Al-Amer et al. (2020)	Specific demographic (Palestinian refugees)	591	PHQ for Adolescents (PHQ-A)	Jordan	Structural validity, internal consistency
Ahmadi et al. (2023)	Clinical population (mental; treatment seeking); Specific demographic (first respondents)	390	Standard PHQ-9	United States of America	Structural validity, hypothesis testing, internal consistency
Aggarwal et al. (2017)	Specific demographic (socioeconomically disadvantaged)	1999	Adolescents (PHQ-9M)	South Africa	Hypothesis testing, internal consistency
Aagard et al. (2023)	Clinical population (physical; chronic pain)	33	Danish version	Denmark	Content validity
Hackett et al. (2019)	Clinical population (mental; attending primary health care services for depression); Specific demographic (Indigenous Australians)	500	aPHQ-9 (Aboriginal English)	Australia	Content validity, hypothesis testing, reliability, internal consistency; Criterion validity
Akena et al. (2013)	Clinical population (physical; HIV positive)	368	Standard PHQ-9; PHQ-2	Uganda	Criterion validity
Aazh et al. (2017)	Clinical population (physical; tinnitus and hyperacusis)	402	Standard PHQ-9	United Kingdom	Feasibility

Insights from the pilot study

Refinement of measurement properties

We expanded data extraction to systematically capture **feasibility** and **interpretability**, which are recognised by COSMIN as important considerations for instrument selection. Feasibility was included to account for factors such as completion rates and modes of administration, which influence the practical use of the instrument in both clinical and research settings. Interpretability was included because the meaning of scores and cut-off values is central to the interpretation of PHQ-9 results and to subsequent clinical or research decisions. Additionally, as an important measurement aspect in the context of PROMs, we included **acceptability** (how respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits) as a stand-alone aspect for which we will collect evidence. Finally, given the large evidence base of studies examining PHQ-9 properties when used as a screening or diagnostic tool, we decided to add Diagnostic and screening accuracy as a specific measurement property to be assessed in these contexts of use of the tool.

Expansion of the search strategy

Based on insights from the pilot phase, the search strategy was refined to improve coverage of relevant psychometric evidence. The COSMIN measurement property filter was adapted and supplemented with additional keywords to allow identification of studies addressing the full range of measurement properties considered in this project, including interpretability, feasibility, and screening accuracy. Additional terms were incorporated for measurement properties that are not consistently retrieved by the original filter. For diagnostic and screening accuracy, terms widely used in the literature such as “predictive value” and “gold standard” were added. Further keywords were included to capture aspects of scale development and content validity (e.g., “patient experience”, “cognitive interviews”), cross-cultural validity and measurement invariance (e.g., “translat*”, “measurement invariance”, “cross-cultural”), and structural validity (e.g., “eigenvalue*”, “RMSEA”). These refinements were made while keeping the COSMIN filter as the basis of the search strategy.

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Appendix B. Operationalization of the Measurement Properties across the Project

The table below provides operational definitions of each measurement property considered in COLIVE-MH, together with practical guidance for reviewers on how to identify relevant evidence in primary studies. For each property, we specify its conceptual definition and indicate the types of analyses, statistics, or study features that reviewers should look for (but not limited to) when extracting and classifying evidence on measurement properties. We also included other properties of the measurement tools that are not measurement properties but constitute important aspects when using a tool (i.e., feasibility, interpretability, acceptability). These definitions do not take into account the context of use (population, purpose) of the measure and are theoretical. Nevertheless, we acknowledge that measurement properties are the product of an interaction between a measurement tool and a population, meaning that these properties might vary across populations. For instance, convergent validity might be correct in a sample of people with diagnosed depression but not in a sample of people with no mental health disorders. The definitions and operationalizations are based on the COSMIN guidelines which is the most comprehensive framework we identified (Mokkink, Elsmann, & Terwee, 2024). However, we acknowledge that measurement science is a dynamic field and that alternative definitions, methods and further progress can be made to conceptualize, assess and interpret measurement properties.

Measurement (and other related) properties	Definitions and Operationalization
1. Content validity	<p>Definition: Content validity is the degree to which the content of an instrument adequately reflects the construct to be measured. It comprises three aspects: relevance (whether items are pertinent to the construct and population), comprehensiveness (whether all key aspects of the construct are covered), and comprehensibility (whether items, instructions, response options, and recall period are understood as intended).</p> <p>Typical indicators: Content validity evidence may come from concept elicitation studies (e.g., qualitative interviews or focus groups) assessing whether all key concepts are represented; from pilot or cognitive interviewing studies assessing comprehensibility of items, instructions, response options, and recall period; or from separate content validity studies in which people with lived experiences or professionals judge relevance, comprehensiveness, and comprehensibility. Analyses may include e.g., content analysis, framework analysis, deductive analysis, or grounded theory.</p>

<p>2. Structural validity</p>	<p>Definition: Structural validity refers to the degree to which the scores of a PROM adequately reflect the dimensionality of the construct to be measured, that is, whether the items group into the expected factor structure or latent model.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Structural validity is commonly evaluated during the development of the measures using principal component analysis (PCA) or exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Structural validity is further confirmed with confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Reported results may include the number of factors, item–factor loadings, explained variance, eigenvalues, model fit indices (e.g., CFI, TLI, RMSEA, SRMR), and tests of model assumptions such as unidimensionality, local independence, monotonicity, or item fit statistics. Item response theory (IRT) or Rasch models can also be used to examine the items in a scale.</p>
<p>3. Internal consistency</p>	<p>Definition: Internal consistency refers to the degree of interrelatedness among items in a scale. It reflects whether items consistently measure the same underlying construct, assuming unidimensionality.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Internal consistency is typically quantified using Cronbach’s alpha, McDonald’s Omega, or IRT/Rasch-based reliability indices (e.g., standard error of theta). Interpretation of these statistics requires evidence that the items form a unidimensional scale, which should be established through prior assessment of structural validity.</p>
<p>4. Cross-cultural validity and measurement invariance</p>	<p>Definition: Cross-cultural validity (or measurement invariance) refers to the extent to which PROM items perform equivalently across different groups, such as languages, cultures, genders, age groups, or clinical populations. It assesses whether individuals with the same underlying level of the construct respond similarly to the items, regardless of group membership.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Cross-cultural validity is commonly evaluated using multi-group factor analysis, including tests of configural, metric, and scalar invariance, or through differential item functioning (DIF) analyses. Studies may also examine longitudinal measurement invariance to assess score comparability over time. Comparisons typically involve culturally or linguistically distinct groups, and may also include other relevant subgroups (e.g., gender, ages etc.).</p>

5. Reliability	<p>Definition: Reliability refers to the proportion of total variance in scores that is due to true differences between individuals. It reflects the ability of an instrument to distinguish between respondents.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Reliability is evaluated using repeated measurements in participants who are expected/assumed to remain stable on the construct. Measurements should be conducted under identical conditions, including the same PROM version, administration mode, response format, and setting, except for the specific source of variation being examined. Most commonly, reliability is assessed over time (test–retest reliability), but studies may also examine consistency across administration modes (e.g., paper vs digital), response formats (e.g., Likert vs VAS), or administrators (e.g., self-report vs interviewer-assisted/read aloud). Reported statistics typically include intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) or kappa values, with specification of the ICC model when applicable. Some studies report Pearson or Spearman correlations, although these are less appropriate for assessing reliability.</p>
6. Measurement error	<p>Definition: Measurement error refers to the systematic and random error in a PROM score that is not attributable to true change in the construct being measured. It refers to the precision of the score. Measurement error is sometimes referred to as agreement and is evaluated using repeated measurements in participants who are assumed to be stable on the construct. The same data collected for the assessment of reliability can be used to evaluate measurement error.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Measurement error is assessed using repeated measurements in stable participants, often drawing on the same study designs used for reliability analyses. Reported statistics may include the standard error of measurement (SEM), smallest detectable change (SDC), limits of agreement (LoA), or percentage agreement for categorical scores. These indices quantify the amount of error around an observed score or change score. Kappa statistics are not measures of measurement error but of reliability.</p>
7. Criterion validity	<p>Definition: Criterion validity refers to the degree to which PROM scores are an adequate reflection of a reference standard (gold standard).</p> <p>Definition by the review team: Upon discussion within the review team, we agreed to define as gold standard the reporting of symptom counts based on clinical diagnostic interviews such as the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM (SCID) or the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI), which assess the same symptoms as those assessed by</p>

	<p>the PHQ-9. Symptom counts based on these interviews are the most reasonable gold standard that is comparable enough to measurement based on self-reporting of depressive symptoms.</p> <p>Psychiatric diagnoses are clinical, meaning that they rely on an interaction between a patient and a clinician. Cut-off thresholds of the PHQ-9 should not be used on its own to establish diagnoses of depressive disorders, given that they do not include all relevant components of diagnostic interviews (e.g., assessment of functional impairment or investigation of other medical conditions that cause similar symptoms; Levis et al., 2020; Thombs et al., 2018). Rather, PHQ-9 thresholds may be used for screening and flagging further assessment for a definitive diagnosis, which includes a clinical judgement. Therefore, it is not reasonable to consider diagnosis as a gold standard for criterion validity of the PHQ-9. The performance of thresholds of the PHQ-9 for screening or as a proxy of diagnosis will be examined on a separate measurement property (8. Diagnostic accuracy).</p>
<p>8. Diagnostic and screening accuracy</p>	<p><u>Definition by the review team</u> The review team will consider the accuracy of the PHQ-9 when evaluated for both diagnostic (diagnosis of the disorder causing the symptoms in clinical population) and screening (identifying unrecognised disorder in non-clinical population) purposes. Diagnostic and screening accuracy can be defined as the ability of a PROM to correctly classify study participants, based on the results, as having the disorder or not (Deeks & Bossuyt, 2023, Chapter 2).</p> <p><u>Typical indicators</u> We will include studies examining the accuracy of the PHQ-9 against a binary diagnostic outcome, defined using a structured or semi-structured clinical interview based on established diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM or ICD). Typical indicators of diagnostic accuracy are: sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values, likelihood ratios, diagnostic odds ratios, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), and 2×2 classification tables. Studies may assess one or multiple cut-off values to examine classification performance across thresholds, often using ROC analyses.</p>
<p>9. Hypothesis testing for construct validity</p>	<p>Definition: Hypothesis testing for construct validity evaluates whether PROM scores behave as expected in relation to other measures or groups, based on a priori hypotheses defined by the review team.</p> <p>Hypotheses formulated by the review team: In the section of Hypothesis testing for construct validity, the PHQ-9 is assessed within the purpose of evaluating symptom severity, and hypotheses are formulated accordingly.</p> <p><u>Using PHQ-9 as a measure of symptom severity</u> Phase A will map the studies reporting on construct validity, and this will provide an overview of the comparator</p>

	<p>instruments used.</p> <p>We expect that for convergent validity, the most common comparators will be the ClinROMs Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D) and the Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) (both ClinROMs recommended by the Food and Drug Administration, FDA), and other widely used PROMs in clinical research, such as Beck Depression Inventory I and II (BDI-I, BDI-II), Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D), Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), and Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), identified by previous systematic reviews (Veal et al., 2024; Sprenger et al., 2026).</p> <p>Further hypotheses for testing construct validity will be specified after the mapping step based on the available comparators. We will consider doing further evidence synthesis (Phase B) on convergent, divergent, and discriminant validity depending on research community needs and available data, discussed with the lived experiences team members and clinicians. Usual indicators reported in the included studies will be correlations between the PHQ-9 total scores and the available comparator measures.</p>
10. Responsiveness	<p>Definition: Responsiveness refers to the ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured. It concerns the accuracy of a change score in relation to a change in the construct measured.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Responsiveness is evaluated by testing <i>a priori</i> hypotheses about expected patterns of change, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Associations between change scores on the PROM and change scores on comparator instruments measuring the same or related constructs. ● Differences in change between groups expected to differ over time (e.g., intervention vs control groups, responders vs non-responders). ● Expected effect sizes following interventions with known or established effects. <p>Hypotheses should specify the expected direction and, where possible, the expected magnitude of change or association. Reported results may include correlations between change scores, mean differences in change, or effect sizes. Statistical significance alone is not sufficient; emphasis is placed on whether observed changes align with predefined hypotheses. Measures such as Guyatt’s responsiveness ratio or MIC/MID are not used to evaluate responsiveness itself, these are measures of interpretability.</p> <p>Hypotheses formulated by the review team:</p> <p><u>PHQ-9</u> Hypotheses are based on the expected direction and magnitude of change scores in the PHQ-9 compared to change scores in other instruments: We expect moderate-to-strong correlations between change scores on</p>

	<p>the PHQ-9 and change scores on established measurements of depression (as a diagnosis or as a continuous measure of symptom severity). We expect that the comparator instruments most commonly found will be the same as those for construct validity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PHQ-9 used for screening or diagnostic purposes: Diagnostic reference standard (e.g., with SCID, MINI, or DSM/ICD-based diagnosis). ● PHQ-9 for assessing symptom severity: other validated measures (PROMs and ClinROMs) commonly used in clinical research for evaluating symptom severity, such as the HAM-D, MADRS, BDI-I, BDI-II, CES-D, EPDS, GDS <p>Phase A will map the studies reporting on responsiveness, and this will provide an overview of the comparator instruments used. Definitive hypotheses for responsiveness will be specified after the mapping step based on the available comparators. As for Hypothesis testing for construct validity, we will synthesise evidence for responsiveness (Phase B) for the most used comparators, based on the needs of the research community and upon discussion with the members of the COLIVE-MH team.</p>
11. Feasibility	<p>Definition: Feasibility refers to the ease of administering the PROM in its intended context, considering practical constraints such as time, burden, cost, and accessibility.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Evidence on feasibility may be reported in studies describing the practical use of the PROM, including information on completion time, number of items, mode of administration, availability of translations, licensing or permission requirements, and implementation-related constraints. Some studies may also report indicators of acceptability or uptake.</p>
12. Interpretability	<p>Definition: Interpretability refers to the degree to which meaningful qualitative information can be assigned to PROM scores or change scores. Interpretability does not evaluate measurement quality itself but provides context for understanding what specific scores or changes represent.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Studies may report the distribution of scores, including floor and ceiling effects, reference values, or cut-off scores indicating severity levels (e.g., mild, moderate, severe). For change scores, studies may report minimal important change (MIC) or minimal important difference (MID), representing the smallest within-person change considered important. Although MIC/MID values are primarily used to interpret change, they are also necessary when evaluating measurement error.</p>

13. Acceptability	<p>Definition: How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Time of completion, number of missing responses, satisfaction with the questionnaire, qualitative reports on the experience of using the scale in research or clinical settings, etc.</p>

Appendix C: Search strings

Block #1: PHQ-9 keywords

("Patient Health Questionnaire"[Mesh] OR "PHQ"[TIAB] OR "PHQ9"[TIAB] OR "patient health questionnaire*" [TIAB] OR "personal health questionnaire*" [TIAB])

Block #2: COSMIN filter

AND ("instrumentation"[sh] OR "methods"[sh] OR "Validation Study"[pt] OR "Comparative Study"[pt] OR "psychometrics"[MeSH] OR "psychometr*" [tiab] OR "clinimetr*" [tw] OR "clinometr*" [tw] OR "Outcome Assessment, Health Care"[Mesh] OR "outcome assessment" [tiab] OR "outcome measure*" [tw] OR "observer variation"[MeSH] OR "observer variation" [tiab] OR "Health Status Indicators"[Mesh] OR "reproducibility of results"[MeSH] OR "reproducib*" [tiab] OR "discriminant analysis"[MeSH] OR "reliab*" [tiab] OR "unreliab*" [tiab] OR "valid*" [tiab] OR "coefficient of variation" [tiab] OR "coefficient" [tiab] OR "homogeneity" [tiab] OR "homogeneous" [tiab] OR "internal consistency" [tiab] OR ("cronbach*" [tiab] AND ("alpha" [tiab] OR "alphas" [tiab])) OR ("item" [tiab] AND ("correlation*" [tiab] OR "selection*" [tiab] OR "reduction*" [tiab])) OR "agreement" [tw] OR "precision" [tw] OR "imprecision" [tw] OR "precise values" [tw] OR "test-retest" [tiab] OR ("test" [tiab] AND "retest" [tiab]) OR ("reliab*" [tiab] AND ("test" [tiab] OR "retest" [tiab])) OR "stability" [tiab] OR "interrater" [tiab] OR "inter-rater" [tiab] OR "intrarater" [tiab] OR "intra-rater" [tiab] OR "intertester" [tiab] OR "inter-tester" [tiab] OR "intratester" [tiab] OR "intra-tester" [tiab] OR "interobserver" [tiab] OR "inter-observer" [tiab] OR "intraobserver" [tiab] OR "intra-observer" [tiab] OR "intertechician" [tiab] OR "inter-technician" [tiab] OR "intratechnician" [tiab] OR "intra-technician" [tiab] OR "interexaminer" [tiab] OR "inter-examiner" [tiab] OR "intraexaminer" [tiab] OR "intra-examiner" [tiab] OR "interassay" [tiab] OR "inter-assay" [tiab] OR "intraassay" [tiab] OR "intra-assay" [tiab] OR "interindividual" [tiab] OR "inter-individual" [tiab] OR "intraindividual" [tiab] OR "intra-individual" [tiab] OR "interparticipant" [tiab] OR "inter-participant" [tiab] OR "intraparticipant" [tiab] OR "intra-participant" [tiab] OR "kappa" [tiab] OR "kappa's" [tiab] OR "kappas" [tiab] OR "repeat*" [tw] OR (("replicab*" [tw] OR "repeated" [tw]) AND ("measure" [tw] OR "measures" [tw] OR "findings" [tw] OR "result" [tw] OR "results" [tw] OR "test" [tw] OR "tests" [tw])) OR "generaliza*" [tiab] OR "generalisa*" [tiab] OR "concordance" [tiab] OR ("intraclass" [tiab] AND "correlation*" [tiab]) OR "discriminative" [tiab] OR "known group" [tiab] OR "factor analysis" [tiab] OR "factor analyses" [tiab] OR "factor structure" [tiab] OR "factor structures" [tiab] OR "dimension*" [tiab] OR "subscale*" [tiab] OR ("multitrait" [tiab] AND "scaling" [tiab] AND ("analysis" [tiab] OR "analyses" [tiab])) OR "item discriminant" [tiab] OR "interscale correlation*" [tiab] OR "error" [tiab] OR "errors" [tiab] OR "individual variability" [tiab] OR "interval variability" [tiab] OR "rate variability" [tiab] OR ("variability" [tiab] AND ("analysis" [tiab] OR "values" [tiab])) OR ("uncertainty" [tiab] AND ("measurement" [tiab] OR "measuring" [tiab])) OR "standard error of measurement" [tiab] OR "sensitiv*" [tiab] OR "responsive*" [tiab] OR ("limit" [tiab] AND "detection" [tiab]) OR "minimal detectable concentration" [tiab] OR "interpret*" [tiab] OR (("minimal" [tiab] OR "minimally" [tiab] OR "clinical" [tiab] OR "clinically" [tiab]) AND ("important" [tiab] OR "significant" [tiab] OR "detectable" [tiab]) AND ("change" [tiab] OR "difference" [tiab])) OR ("small*" [tiab] AND ("real" [tiab] OR "detectable" [tiab]) AND ("change" [tiab] OR "difference" [tiab])) OR "meaningful change" [tiab] OR "ceiling effect" [tiab] OR "floor effect" [tiab] OR "Item response

model"[tiab] OR "IRT"[tiab] OR "Rasch"[tiab] OR "Differential item functioning"[tiab] OR "DIF"[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "item bank"[tiab] OR "cross-cultural equivalence"[tiab])

Block #3: Additional words specifically about diagnostic accuracy

OR ("index test"[tiab] OR "reference test"[tiab] OR "reference standard"[tiab] OR "gold standard"[tiab] OR "structured clinical interview"[tiab] OR "diagnostic accuracy"[tiab:~2] OR "DTA"[tiab] OR "predictive value"[tiab] OR "PPV"[tiab] OR "NPV"[tiab] OR "positive predictive value"[tiab] OR "negative predictive value"[tiab] OR "likelihood ratio"[tiab] OR "sensitivity"[ti] OR "specificity"[ti] OR "cut-off"[tiab] OR "cutoff"[tiab] OR "cut point"[tiab] OR "threshold score"[tiab] OR "ROC"[tiab] OR "receiver* operating characteristic"[tiab] OR "AUC"[tiab] OR "area* under the curve"[tiab] OR "case detection"[tiab] OR "case finding"[tiab] OR "classification"[tiab])

Block #4: Additional words about all measurement properties

OR ("Patient* experience"[tiab] OR "Patient* involvement"[tiab] OR "Patient* input"[tiab] OR "Patient* perception"[tiab] OR "User* feedback"[tiab] OR "Patient* feedback"[tiab] OR "Cognitive interview"[tiab] OR "Clinician* perception"[tiab] OR "Pilot testing"[tiab] OR "Field testing"[tiab] OR "Focus Groups"[Mesh] OR "Focus group"[tiab] OR "Cognitive debriefing"[tiab] OR "Expert* panel"[tiab] OR "Expert* review"[tiab] OR "Comprehensibility"[tiab] OR "Comprehensiveness"[tiab] OR "Item wording"[tiab] OR "Item evaluation"[tiab] OR "Item relevance"[tiab] OR "Item clarity"[tiab] OR "Item analy"[tiab] OR "Gold standard"[tiab] OR "Area under curve"[tiab] OR "Area under a curve"[tiab] OR "Translat"[tiab] OR "Measurement invariance"[tiab] OR "Cross-cultural"[tiab] OR "Back-translation"[tiab] OR "Forward-translation"[tiab] OR "Cross-group equivalence"[tiab] OR "Linguistic validation"[tiab] OR "Measurement equivalence"[tiab] OR "Semantic equivalence"[tiab] OR "Conceptual equivalence"[tiab] OR "measure* propert"[tiab] OR "CAT"[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "Scale development"[tiab] OR "Reflective model"[tiab] OR "Formative model"[tiab] OR "Measurement model"[tiab] OR "Classical test theory"[tiab] OR "Scoring algorithm"[tiab] OR "Instrument development"[tiab] OR "Questionnaire development"[tiab] OR "McDonald* omega"[tiab] OR "Omega coefficient"[tiab] OR "Item-total correlation"[tiab] OR "Reference score"[tiab] OR "Perceived change"[tiab] OR "smallest worthwhile effect"[tiab] OR "LoA"[tiab] OR "SDC"[tiab] OR "MIC"[tiab] OR "intraclass correlation coefficient"[tiab] OR "ICC"[tiab] OR "item characteristic curve"[tiab] OR (("eigenvalue"[tiab] OR "CFI"[tiab] OR "CFA"[tiab] OR "comparative fit index"[tiab] OR "TFI"[tiab] OR "tucker lewis index"[tiab] OR "RMSEA"[tiab] OR "root mean square error of approximation"[tiab] OR "SRMR"[tiab] OR "standardized root mean square residual"[tiab] OR "WRMR"[tiab] OR "weighted root mean square residual"[tiab] OR "ECV"[tiab] OR "explained common variance"[tiab] OR "PCA"[tiab] OR "component analy"[tiab]) AND ("factor"[tiab] OR "item"[tiab])) OR "items factors"[tiab] OR "Item response theory"[tiab] OR "Kaiser criterion"[tiab] OR "Factor loadings"[tiab] OR "One-factor model"[tiab] OR "Two-factor model"[tiab] OR "Bifactor model"[tiab] OR "Bi-factor model"[tiab] OR "Localindependence"[tiab] OR "Monotonicity"[tiab] OR "Unidimensional"[tiab] OR ("item"[tiab] AND ("correlation"[tiab] OR "selection"[tiab] OR "reduction"[tiab])) OR "Floor effect"[tiab] OR "Ceiling effect"[tiab] OR "hypothes* test"[tiab] OR "convergent"[tiab] OR "discriminant"[tiab] OR "known-groups"[tiab])

Block #5: COSMIN exclusion filter, with adaptations

NOT ("address"[Publication Type] OR "biography"[Publication Type] OR "case reports"[Publication Type] OR "comment"[Publication Type] OR "directory"[Publication Type] OR "editorial"[Publication Type] OR "festschrift"[Publication Type] OR "interview"[Publication Type] OR "lecture"[Publication Type] OR "legal case"[Publication Type] OR "legislation"[Publication Type] OR "letter"[Publication Type] OR "news"[Publication Type] OR "newspaper article"[Publication Type] OR "patient education handout"[Publication Type] OR "popular work"[Publication Type] OR "congress"[Publication Type] OR "consensus development conference"[Publication Type] OR "consensus development conference, nih"[Publication Type] OR "practice guideline"[Publication Type])

NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms])

Block #6: Time limits

AND ("1995/01/01"[Date - Publication] : "2026/01/20"[Date - Publication])

Selecting 1995 as the lower end allows us to have a security margin of 4 years, the oldest scale being the PHQ-9 with a first paper published in 1999.

Reference for the COSMIN filter:

Terwee, C. B., Jansma, E. P., Riphagen, I. I., & de Vet, H. C. (2009). Development of a methodological PubMed search filter for finding studies on measurement properties of measurement instruments. *Quality of Life Research*, 18(8), 1115-1123.

Appendix D: Codebook for data extraction in Phase A (Living Mapping of the Evidence)

Category	Variable name	Variable definition	Permissible values
Study metadata	DOI	Digital Object Identifier	Alphanumeric DOI string
	Database identifier	Unique identifier assigned to the study by the database in which it is indexed (e.g., PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase)	PMID (numeric), Web of Science Accession Number (alphanumeric), Embase ID (alphanumeric), or another database-specific identifier.
	Author	Surname of the first author of the study	First author surname followed by <i>et al.</i> (if applicable)
	Year of publication	Calendar year in which the study was published	Four-digit year (e.g., 2018)
	Journal	Name of the journal in which the article was published	Alphanumeric
	Article ID	Unique identifier assigned to the article within the review	Review-assigned article ID (Alphanumeric string)
	Sample ID	Unique identifier assigned within the review to each unique sample in the article (if multiple samples)	Review-assigned sample ID Not applicable
Study characteristics	Study methodological approach	Study methodological approach based on the nature of the data collected and the analytic methods used.	Quantitative
			Qualitative
			Mixed-methods
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Study design	Type of methodological design used in the study	Observational – Cross-sectional
			Observational – Longitudinal Prospective
			Observational – Longitudinal Retrospective
			Observational – Longitudinal (Timing Not Reported)
			Interventional – Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)
			Interventional – Non-randomized Trial /quasi-experimental
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Inclusion criteria with threshold	Indicate if the participants of the study were included according to a continuous threshold	Yes
			No
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
PROM characteristics	Patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) used	Name of the PROM used in the study that is within the scope of this review (If a study uses more than one eligible PROM, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each PROM)	GAD7 (7-item anxiety scale)
			PHQ9 (9-item depression scale)
			RCADS 25
			WHODAS 36-item
			WHODAS 12-item (short form)
			WHODAS 12+24-item
	Scoring computation	Method used to calculate WHODAS 2.0	Simple scoring

	method (only for WHODAS)	scores: simple (unweighted sum), complex (IRT-weighted)	Complex scoring
			Not applicable
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Item wording modifications	Indicate whether the item wording has been modified from the original validated version of the instrument	Yes
			No
	Detail item wording modifications	Specify which changes were made to the item wording	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Response scoring modifications	Indicate whether the response scoring has been modified from the original validated version of the instrument	Yes
			No
	Detail response scoring modifications	Specify which changes were made to the response scoring	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 1	Name of other instrument used in the study (to be completed if the study assessed any measurement property of another listed instrument in addition to the main eligible PROM)	GAD2 (2-item anxiety screener)
			PHQ2 (2-item depression screener)
PHQ4 (4-item combined anxiety/depression screener)			
PHQ5 (5-item short form)			
PHQ8 (8-item depression scale (no suicidality item))			
RCADS 11			
RCADS 25			
RCADS 47			

			WHODAS 36-item
			WHODAS 12-item (short form)
			WHODAS 12+24-item
			Other (specify)
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 1 (other)	Specify the name of the instrument when "Other (specify)" is selected for the variable Other PROM 1	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 2	Name of other instrument used in the study (to be completed if the study assessed any measurement property of another listed instrument in addition to the main eligible PROM)	GAD2 (2-item anxiety screener)
			PHQ2 (2-item depression screener)
			PHQ4 (4-item combined anxiety/depression screener)
			PHQ5 (5-item short form)
			PHQ8 (8-item depression scale (no suicidality item))
			RCADS 11
			RCADS 25
			RCADS 47
WHODAS 36-item			
WHODAS 12-item (short form)			
WHODAS 12+24-item			
Other (specify)			
Not applicable			

	Other PROM 2 (other)	Specify the name of the instrument when "Other (specify)" is selected for the variable Other PROM 2	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Administration mode	Mode of administration indicating the informant of the scale	Self-reported version
			Caregiver report version (RCADS only)
			Interviewer version eliciting patient perspective
	Completion assistance	If the respondent requires assistance to complete the scale (without judgement or influence of the person assisting the application of the instrument), which type of assistance is provided to the target individual (informant) during completion of the scale	No assistance
			Interviewer-assisted
			Caregiver-assisted
			Clinician-assisted
			Other (specify)
	Completion assistance (other)	Description of the type of completion assistance when "Other (specify)" is selected for the variable Completion assistance	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Medium of administration	Format or medium used to deliver the scale	Paper and pencil
			Digital device (any)
			Telephone interview
			Other (specify)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Medium of administration (other)	Description of the medium of administration when "Other (specify)" is selected for the variable Medium of administration	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable

	Purpose of using the scale	Context of use of the PROM in which the measurement properties were evaluated	Diagnostic/screening
			Outcome assessment
			Other (specify)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Language	Language in which the PROM is administered (as reported in the article)	Alphanumeric string
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Participants' characteristics	Description of the study sample	Description of the included study sample as shown in the article	Alphanumeric string
	Age group of the study sample	Age category of the study sample as reported in the article, based on the age range or mean age of participants	Adults
			Adolescents
			Adults and adolescents
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Sample size	Total number of participants included in the study/analysis	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Minimum age (inclusion criteria)	Lower eligible age threshold	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Maximum age (inclusion criteria)	Upper eligible age threshold	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Minimum age (study sample)	Youngest age among participants included in the study	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Maximum age (study sample)	Oldest age among participants included in the study	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Mean age of the study sample	Mean (average) age of the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Age standard deviation of the study sample	Standard deviation of age within the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Median age of the study sample	Median age within the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Number of male participants	Total number of male participants included in the study	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Number of female participants	Total number of female participants included in the study	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Sex distribution	Percentage of study participants who are female, as reported or calculable from the study (use the proportion reported by the authors or calculate it from provided sex distribution data when available)	Alphanumeric string. Percentage of male and female participants
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Gender distribution	Percentage of participants categorized by gender identity (e.g., man, woman, non-binary), if defined or implied in the study, based on self-identification or explicit gender measures	Alphanumeric string. Percentage of participants self-identified as man, woman, non-binary or other (specify the percentage for each reported gender).
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Type of population	General classification of the population studied	Clinical (physical health conditions)
			Clinical (mental health conditions)
			Clinical (substance-use disorders)
			Healthy volunteer (with no diagnosed conditions)
			General population (community sample)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Category physical health condition 1	Primary category describing the physical health condition present in the study population, if applicable	Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)	

			Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)
			Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)
			Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)
			Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)
			Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)
			Cancer / oncological conditions
			Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)
			Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)
			Renal and urological diseases
			Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)
			Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)
			Other physical health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

			Not applicable
Name of the physical health condition 1	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors		Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Diagnostic basis physical health condition 1	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants		Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Definition physical health condition 1	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions		Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Category physical health condition 2	Primary category describing an additional physical health condition present in the study population when multiple physical conditions		Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)

		<p>are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition.</p>	<p>Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)</p> <p>Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)</p> <p>Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)</p> <p>Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)</p> <p>Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)</p> <p>Cancer / oncological conditions</p> <p>Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)</p> <p>Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)</p> <p>Renal and urological diseases</p> <p>Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)</p> <p>Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)</p> <p>Other physical health condition</p> <p>Unclear – lack of reporting</p> <p>Unclear – don't know/don't understand</p>
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			Not applicable
Name of the physical health condition 2	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors		Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Diagnostic basis physical health condition 2	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants		Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Definition physical health condition 2	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions		Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Category physical health condition 3	Primary category describing an additional physical health condition present in the study population when multiple physical conditions		Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)

		<p>are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition</p>	<p>Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)</p> <p>Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)</p> <p>Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)</p> <p>Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)</p> <p>Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)</p> <p>Cancer / oncological conditions</p> <p>Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)</p> <p>Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)</p> <p>Renal and urological diseases</p> <p>Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)</p> <p>Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)</p> <p>Other physical health condition</p> <p>Unclear – lack of reporting</p> <p>Unclear – don't know/don't understand</p>
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			Not applicable
	Name of the physical health condition 3	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis physical health condition 3	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition physical health condition 3	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category mental health condition 1	Primary category describing the mental health condition present in the study population, if applicable	Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)
			Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)

			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)
			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
			Name of the mental health condition 1
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Not applicable			
Diagnostic basis mental health condition 1	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)	

		participants	Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition mental health condition 1	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category mental health condition 2	Primary category describing an additional mental health condition present in the study population when multiple mental health conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition	Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)
			Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)

			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the mental health condition 2	Specific mental health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., major depressive disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis mental health condition 2	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
Self-reported diagnosis			
Screening tool			
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Not applicable			
Definition mental health	Operational or clinical definition of the mental	Alphanumeric string	

	condition 2	health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category mental health condition 3	Primary category describing an additional mental health condition present in the study population when multiple mental health conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition	Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)
			Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)
			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Not applicable			

	Name of the mental health condition 3	Specific mental health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., major depressive disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis mental health condition 3	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition mental health condition 3	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 1	Primary category describing the substance-use disorder present in the study population, if applicable	Alcohol use disorder
Tobacco / nicotine use disorder			
Cannabis use disorder			
Opioid use disorder			

			Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)
			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the substance-use disorder 1	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 1	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition substance-use	Operational or clinical definition of the	Alphanumeric string

	disorder 1	substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 2	Primary category describing an additional substance-use disorder present in the study population when multiple substance-use disorders are reported as coexistent. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different substance-use disorders using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each disorder	Alcohol use disorder
			Tobacco / nicotine use disorder
			Cannabis use disorder
			Opioid use disorder
			Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)
			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
	Unclear – don't know/don't understand		
Not applicable			
Name of the substance-use disorder 2	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
		Not applicable	
Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 2	Method used to determine the presence of the	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)	

	substance-use disorder among participants	Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)	
		Self-reported diagnosis	
		Screening tool	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
		Not applicable	
	Definition substance-use disorder 2	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 3	Primary category describing an additional substance-use disorder present in the study population when multiple substance-use disorders are reported as coexistent. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different substance-use disorders using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each disorder	Alcohol use disorder
			Tobacco / nicotine use disorder
			Cannabis use disorder
			Opioid use disorder
			Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)
			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			

			Not applicable
Name of the substance-use disorder 3	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors		Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 3	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants		Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Definition substance-use disorder 3	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions		Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Specific demographics	Identification of specific demographic subgroups targeted in the study		Veterans
			LGBTQIA+
			Migrants

			Other (specify)
	Geographical setting	Geographic location where the study was conducted	Country or countries
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Healthcare setting level	Level of healthcare system in which the study was conducted	Primary care
			Secondary care
			Tertiary care
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Patient setting	Care context in which participants received services or were studied	Outpatient
			Inpatient
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
PROM construct and assessed measurement properties in the study	PROM construct	Construct that the PROM is intended to assess, as explicitly stated by the study authors	Alphanumeric string. Construct description using authors' wording (e.g., quality of life, physical functioning, pain intensity, mental health, symptom severity, etc.)
	Content validity*	The degree to which the content of a PROM is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting

			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Structural validity*	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Internal consistency*	The degree of the interrelatedness among the items.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Cross-cultural validity / measurement invariance*	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted PROM are an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the PROM.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Reliability*	The extent to which scores for respondents who have not changed are the same for repeated measurement under several conditions: e.g., using different sets of items from the same PROM (internal consistency); over time (test-retest); by different persons on the same occasion (inter-rater); or by the same persons (i.e., raters or responders) on different occasions (intra-rater).	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Measurement error*	The systematic and random error of a respondent's score that is not attributed to	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed

		true changes in the construct to be measured.	Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Criterion validity*	Criterion validity refers to the degree to which PROM scores are an adequate reflection of a reference standard (gold standard).	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Comparator instrument for criterion validity	If results for criterion validity are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator	Alphanumeric string.
			Not applicable
	Hypothesis testing for construct validity*	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are consistent with hypotheses (with regard to relationships to scores of other instruments, or differences between relevant groups) based on the assumption that the PROM validly measures the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Comparator instrument for hypothesis testing for construct validity	If results for hypothesis testing for construct validity are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator	Alphanumeric string.
			Not applicable
Responsiveness*	The ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results	
		Not assessed	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
Comparator instrument for Responsiveness	If results for Responsiveness are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator	Alphanumeric string.	
		Not applicable	

Other properties of the measurement tools	Feasibility*	Ease of application of the PROM in its intended context of use, given constraints such as time or money.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Interpretability*	The degree to which one can assign qualitative meaning - that is, clinical or commonly understood connotations – to a PROM's quantitative scores or change in scores.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Acceptability	How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
Involvement of lived-experience contributors	Involvement of lived-experience contributors	Indicate whether individuals with lived experience actively contributed to the study.	Yes
			No
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

* Definition derived from the COSMIN taxonomy, as specified in the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024).